

REPRESENTATION OF AUTHOR'S MODALITY IN A LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT

Modality, the way of revealing writer's attitude towards events and heroes of a literary text, is divided into epistemic and root types, which differ from the usage of words and stylistic devices. Stylistic devices have always been essential for selecting the modality including the variability of text genres. The research is aimed at determining how the stylistic devices help to express modality in a literary text.

Two short stories which have similar plot, yet the expression of the events totally different, are chosen to analyze the attitude of authors. The stories are written by O. Henry and Abdulla Kakhkhor, which is different in language of author as A. Kakhkhor uses proverbs, phrases to express his opinion about situation while O. Henry is fond of making unexpected ending for the reader.

As a result of the research, the epistemic type of modality make reader feel the narrator in the events or situations. The epistemic modality is mostly addressed in the short stories that are analyzed. The writer's confidence and outlook is activated by perception of external appearances or surroundings.

Introduction

Modality in a literary text is investigated from two basic ways of revealing writer's attitude. First way is learning the use of modal verbs and their role in expression of modality. Second way is studying and analyzing the literary text through stylistic devices and style of representing author's modality by his phrases, expression of the nature, manner of people, their surroundings and so on.

Many researchers and linguistics studied several methods of representing author's modality in a literary text. According to Palmer (2003) there are three categories of modality named epistemic, dynamic and deontic. He considers that epistemic modality reveals the writer's attitude to status of the proposition, while dynamic and deontic modalities express the consent to the occurrence of the action or situation.

(Palmer 2003, p.7). However, deontic is concerned with the circumstances external to the subject of the sentence, while with dynamic, the control is internal and the subject's personal ability of doing something is included (Palmer 2003, p. 7).

Examples of these modalities are:

1. They may be on their way. (epistemic)
2. You can report now. (deontic)
3. You can eat a lot. (dynamic)

The modal may in example 1 show that the speaker is uncertain whether they, the subject in the sentence, are leaving or not. The modal can in the next two examples are expressed differently in these sentences. In the second example, the can is controlled by the speaker 's permission (external), whereas in the third example, the can is controlled by the subject (internal). In order to better comprehend the literary novels Palmer (2003), Simpson (2004) also discussed modality according to points of view. According to Simpson, modality is concerned with the attitude and ability of the persona/narrator. It also refers broadly to a speaker's attitude towards, or opinion about, the truth of a proposition expressed by a sentence. It also extends to the speaker's attitude towards the situation or event described by a sentence (Simpson 1993, p. 43).

Admittedly, modality which is used in the story represents feelings, thoughts and meaning of the whole literary work. There are also different shades of modality called positive, negative and neutral which was characterized by Simpson (2004). Abundant use of deontic and boulomaic modalities falls under the positive and as Iwamoto (2007) says, the general flow of discourse of this type is binding, obligatory, assertive, and strong (p.181). Preponderant

use of epistemic and perception modalities, however, give off negative shading that denotes alienation and uncertainty. Neutral shading is characterized by the absence of modality or modal judgment that exhibits an uncommitted and detached connotation (Iwamoto 2007, p.181) in discourse. Deontic modality is the modal system of duty as it is concerned with speaker's attitude to the degree of obligation attached to the performance of certain actions. In short, deontic modal auxiliaries realize a continuum of commitment from (a) permission, such as (4) you may take your seat; (b), through obligation, such as (5) you should be finished before lunch time; and (c), and requirement, such as (6) you must finish your degree (Simpson, 1993, p.43).

Discussion

The perception of modality is a wide sense reflecting the different attitude by the writer. The types of modality can be identified through the analysis of the literary works.

Epistemic modality is the third type of modality which shows the author's confidence or less confidence towards the situation. Mostly, it is represented through the modal lexical verbs. For example, I presume you are right. Moreover, adjectives also used in epistemic modality, like:

- a) I am certain to be right
- b) I am definite that I am right.

It should be noted that there is a number of modal adverbs which is included, but not restricted to use: arguably, maybe, perhaps, possibly, probably, certainly, supposedly, allegedly. (Simpson 1993, p. 45)

These categories of modality are being observed through short stories. Although the stories "Last leaf" and

“Bemor” (Patient) encompasses similar meaning and idea, the modality of the writers are totally different. “Bemor” begins with epigraph expressing impossibility. “*Osmon yiroq – yer qattiq*” (“Bemor”, A.Khahhor, page 1) – it is translated into English as: *the sky is too high; the earth is too solid*. This proverb is utilized by Uzbek people when they are really in a difficult situation.

Furthermore, “*Bularning hammasi, albatta, pul bilan bo'ladi*” (“Bemor”, A.Khahhor, page 2) – “*This all, definitely requires money*”, this passage shows epistemic modality as the author expresses his opinion with confidence. In addition, adverbial modal – definitely, is addressed to represent his opinion.

Next story, “Last leaf” is about a girl Johnny who was ill with pneumonia and she thought that if the last leaf of the ivy tree which is seen from her window fell she would also die in this moment. This story is written by O. Henry who is popular with unexpected ending short stories.

Epistemic modality is frequently used in this story too. For instance,

- *Young artists must work their way to “Art” by making pictures for magazine stories.* (“Last leaf”, O.Henry)

Here, writer shows his attitude with modal verb “must” and it informs the reader that he strongly confident about this position. And it is obviously seen that the writer represented it by epistemic modality.

Conclusion

All in all, these two writers use different language and style, they both mostly addressed to the epistemic category of modality. Modality is represented by adverbs, auxiliaries and modal verbs as well. This category is very important in text linguistics as it helps analyze and open the author’s role in a written work. Throughout the analysis of short stories, the epistemic modality is seen to be mostly used. Therefore, the final results of this article sums up that the epistemic type of modality makes author in the center of the events and for this reason it is utilized more frequently.

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